

The Descriptive Value and the Normative Force of the Preambles of the Treaties making up the European Social Charter System

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Abstract:

Revisiting the Preamble of the European Social Charter (ESC) does not entail examining a single text: The Charter system is composed of five different treaties. Thus, this paper explores, recital by recital, the historical significance and descriptive value of the Preambles in the ESC system and assesses what their normative role is or could be. This twofold analysis is presented in three core sections that relate to the Preambles of 1) the ESC of 1961; 2) the Protocols of 1988, 1991 and 1995; 3) and the Revised Charter of 1996, respectively. The conclusions show that the Preambles of this treaty system represent a rich source of heterogeneous information on the historical motives and ideals that led to the drafting of the treat(ies), the system's revitalisation needs and the substantive and procedural reform steps that have been undertaken. They can also exercise normative force by adding interpretative nuance and filling gaps that may exist in the main text of the Charter(s).

Keywords: European Social Charter, Preamble, Socioeconomic Rights, Treaty Interpretation, Council of Europe

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I. Introductory Remarks

The European Social Charter (ESC) is the “counterpart” or “sister treaty” of the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR) in the socio-economic field.¹ With purpose of highlighting its centrality in the European human rights framework, the Council of Europe (CoE) often defines it as the “Social Constitution of Europe”.²

Revisiting the Preamble to the ESC does not entail examining the wording, intentions, and potential normative value of a single treaty text: The ESC system comprises several formal CoE treaties, each with a different preamble. These treaties are the European Social Charter, signed on 18 October 1961 (hereafter referred to as the “Charter of 1961” or “original Charter”); the Additional Protocol of 1988, which extended the socio-economic rights of the Charter of 1961; the 1991 “Turin Protocol”, which revised some of the rules governing the reporting procedures of the European

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¹ Jean-François Akandji-Kombe, «The Material Impact of the Jurisprudence of the European Committee of Social Rights», in: G. De Búrca & B. De Witte (eds.), *Social Rights in Europe*, OUP, Oxford 2005, 89–108, at 89, 90; David Harris, «A Fresh Impetus for the European Social Charter», 41(3) *The International and Comparative Law Review* (1992), 659–676, at 659.

² For instance, see High-Level Conference on the European Social Charter, «General Report», Turin, 17–18 October 2014, at 4 <<https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=090000168048acf8>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

Committee of Social Rights (ECSR); the 1995 Additional Protocol, which provided for a system of collective complaints; and the Revised European Social Charter, which was adopted and opened for ratification in 1996 (Revised Charter).³ All these instruments are formally independent of each other, and the Charter of 1961 – with its 19 substantive rights that were formulated and agreed upon in the late 1950s – continues to operate as a valid standard-setting instrument for those six CoE states who are not parties to the Revised Charter of 1996.⁴

Both versions of the Charter contain a noteworthy level of detail on state obligations regarding socio-economic rights of both an immediate and progressive nature,⁵ but, in general, they are normatively weaker instruments than the ECHR for a number of reasons: First, neither Charter is entirely binding on state parties upon ratification; rather, states can select a minimum number of articles or paragraphs to which they choose to be bound and which include some core provisions.⁶ However, Part I of both versions of the Charter clarifies that the attainment of the conditions in which all substantive Charter rights can be realised must constitute a programmatic policy objective for all state parties. Second, the personal scope of the Charters textually extends only to the nationals of the member states, although this paper will explain how the principles of the indivisibility of all human rights and of systematic interpretation of treaty obligations – also endorsed in the treaty preamble(s) – have partially addressed this limitation.⁷ Third, from a monitoring and accountability perspective, the Charter system provides for forms of collective accountability for social rights before the ECSR, via a compulsory periodic reporting procedure and an optional collective complaint mechanism, rather than a right to individual petitions.⁸

All the above factors result from compromises between the different views of European states regarding the non-European-only dilemma that prevailed during the second half of 20th Century on whether it was desirable to establish international standards and supervisory legal or quasi-legal mechanisms for the protection of socio-economic rights. It is worth noting that at the time when the ECHR had just begun to enter into force, early discussions among the CoE bodies were centred on the need for a “common policy in the social field”⁹ or “common principles of social progress”¹⁰ to realise the key aims of the organisation.¹¹ A couple of years into the negotiations, the bodies entrusted with the drafting of the Charter eventually decided it would contain both policy objectives and obligations binding in law.¹²

³ European Social Charter (ESC) (adopted 18 October 1996, entry into force 1961) ETS No. 035; Additional protocol to the European Social Charter (adopted 5 May 1988, entry into force 4 September 1992) ETS. No. 128; Protocol amending the European Social Charter (adopted 21 October 1991), applied via CM/Del/Concl(91), ETS. No. 142; Additional Protocol to the European Social Charter providing for a system of collective complaints (adopted 9 November 1995, entry into force 1 July 1997) ETS No. 158; European Social Charter (revised) (adopted 3 May 1996, entry into force 1 July 1999) ETS No. 163.

⁴ As of May 2021, of the 43 states that have ratified the European Social Charter, only Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Iceland, Luxembourg, Poland, and the United Kingdom are parties to the original Charter of 1961. The remainder are parties to the Revised Charter of 1996, see <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/signatures-ratifications>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

⁵ See *infra*, Section IV on the nature of obligations.

⁶ ESC, *supra* n. 3, Part III, Article 20; ESC (revised), *supra* n. 3, Part III, Article A.

⁷ See *infra*, Section IV.

⁸ Holly Cullen, «The Collective Complaints System of the European Social Charter: Interpretative Methods of the European Committee of Social Rights», 9(1) Human Rights Law Review (2009), 61–93, at 66.

⁹ PACE, Recommendation n. 14 «Adoption by Member States of the Council of Europe of a common policy in social matters», 1951.

¹⁰ Memorandum by the Secretariat General of the Council of Europe on the role of the Council of Europe in the social field SC (53) 1, Strasbourg, 16 April 1953, in: «Collected edition of the travaux préparatoires» Vol. I, 1953–1954.

¹¹ Statute of the Council of Europe (Adopted 5 May 1949, entry into force 3 August 1949) ETS No. 1, Article 1. Further analysis on this point is developed *infra* in Section II.

¹² Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe, Resolution (56) 25 «European Social Charter», 15 December 1956.

Against this background and the particularities of the Charter system, this paper poses two main questions: What historical or descriptive significance do the preambles in ESC system hold? What normative role do they play in the treaty context? To answer these questions, this paper conducts a textual analysis of the recitals of the ESC Preambles, in the light of the ESCR jurisprudence, the *travaux préparatoires* of the Charter and scholarly material. This examination is presented in the three sections that, although they are interconnected, concern, respectively, 1) the Charter of 1961; 2) the Protocols of 1988, 1991 and 1995; and 3) the Revised Charter. The Preambles to the treaties composing the ESC system are an important part of these legal instruments because, as is the case with other human rights treaties, they “add texture and nuance, to place the treaty within its historical context, and [...] to offer guides for interpreters”, either states or international supervisory bodies.¹³

This is particularly important if we consider the potential range of roles that these Preambles can perform in the interpretation of the Charter as an instrument of international law. The common meaning of a preamble is a “preliminary statement in a speech or writing”; in law, it refers to an “introductory paragraph or section of [a legal document] setting out its intention, scope”.¹⁴ With respect to international law, the notion of a preamble is generally associated with “the purposes and considerations [...] motivation ... intention [...] that led the parties to conclude the treaty”, a definition that conforms to the Preambles to the ESC treaties.¹⁵ On whether the Preambles are merely ceremonial statements or whether they play an actual role in treaty interpretation, the Vienna Convention of the Law of the Treaties (VCLT), which codifies customary international law, explicitly attributes legal value to the Preambles, which are deemed to contribute to text–context analysis for the interpretation of the scope of rights and obligations within a treaty.¹⁶ In practice, preambles of treaties are “generally very useful for the determination of the <object> and <purpose> of the instrument”.¹⁷ The preambles of the European Social Charter seems suitable to be assessed against various non-exclusionary normative functions that preambles may play in international law:¹⁸ an overall *interpretative* function with respect to state obligations relating to the substantive rights of the Charter resulting from an “object and purpose” analysis; an *incorporative* function in relation to the values and norms of other treaties that, as a result of incorporation clauses, may extend the scope of the Charter-based obligations; and a *supplementary* function aimed at filling the normative gaps in the main text or the operative part of the Charter, which, in the case of the Charter of 1961, includes the non-discrimination principle.

II. The Charter of 1961 – Back to the Beginnings

To go back to the beginnings with the purpose of revisiting the Preambles of the ESC, it is worth examining how the ESC came to life within the CoE’s normative framework. To this end, it is necessary to clarify that both the Consultative Assembly of the CoE (now the Parliamentary Assembly, PACE) and the Committee of Ministers of the CoE were, between 1954 and 1960, deeply involved in the drafting of their respective versions of a treaty that established socio-economic

¹³ William Shabas, «Preamble/Préambule», in: W. Shabas, *The European Convention on Human Rights: A Commentary*, OUP, Oxford 2015, 53–83, at 54.

¹⁴ Oxford English Dictionary, «Preamble», <<https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/149489?rskey=7qPbbP&result=1#eid>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

¹⁵ Makane Moïse Mbengue, «Preamble» in: Max Planck Encyclopaedia of Public International Law, last update 2006.

¹⁶ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT) (adopted 23 May 1969 entry into force 27 January 1980) 1155 UNTS 331, Article 31: “1. A treaty shall be interpreted in good faith in accordance with the ordinary meaning to be given to the terms of the treaty in their context and in the light of its object and purpose. 2. The context for the purpose of the interpretation of a treaty shall comprise, in addition to the text, including its preamble and annexes [...]”.

¹⁷ ECtHR, *Golder v the United Kingdom*, Appl. No. 4451/70, judgment of 21 February 1975, para 34; See also Max Hulme, «Preambles in Treaty Interpretation», 126 *University of Pennsylvania Law Review* (2016), 1281–1343, at 1300.

¹⁸ This classification is partly based upon that of Mbengue, *supra* n. 15.

objectives and rights.¹⁹ The need to set out common principles of the organisation and of member states' actions in the socio-economic sphere emerged within the PACE as early as 1951, and the idea of a social charter was eventually approved by this body in 1953.²⁰ However, it must be said that the final text of the ESC mainly reflects the work of the Social Committee of the Committee of Ministers, which was the body entrusted with this task by the governments of the CoE member states. However, the Social Committee's final draft was partially improved as a result of the PACE's suggestions for modifications, which incorporated discussions that took place in a "Tripartite Conference" (composed of government, employer and worker delegates) convened in 1958.²¹

The Preamble to the original Charter is based on a proposal submitted by the UK delegation to the Social Committee in 1956.²² It is a short preamble, and this was considered desirable by most delegates because detailed principles of socio-economic policies would be listed in Part I of the draft Charter.²³ This UK proposal was subjected to some rewording before the final text was adopted in 1961, the most notable accepted revision being the inclusion of a recital which prohibited discrimination in the enjoyment of social rights, as recommended by the PACE in 1959.²⁴

Table 1. The Preamble of the European Social Charter of 1961 (ETS. No. 35)	
1	The governments signatory hereto, being members of the Council of Europe,
2	Considering that the aim of the Council of Europe is the achievement of greater unity between its members for the purpose of safeguarding and realising the ideals and principles which are their common heritage and of facilitating their economic and social progress, in particular by the maintenance and further realisation of human rights and fundamental freedoms;
3	Considering that in the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms signed at Rome on 4th November 1950, and the Protocol thereto signed at Paris on 20th March 1952, the member States of the Council of Europe agreed to secure to their populations the civil and political rights and freedoms therein specified;
4	Considering that the enjoyment of social rights should be secured without discrimination on grounds of race, colour, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction or social origin;
5	Being resolved to make every effort in common to improve the standard of living and to promote the social well-being of both their urban and rural populations by means of appropriate institutions and action,
6	Have agreed as follows:

A. The Council of Europe treaty on socioeconomic values, interests, policies and rights

The first recital of the Preamble of the Charter coincides with that of the ECHR and emphasises the signature of the document as a landmark event in the life of the treaty, although the Charter acknowledges that this is only a preliminary act to the acceptance of its legal obligations, which involves ratification under Article 35 ESC. The Charter was opened for signature by the CoE member states in Palazzo Madama, in Turin, on 18 October 1961. On the very same day, all CoE member

¹⁹ See «Collected Travaux Préparatoires» <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/preparatory-work>>, an overview of which is offered by David Harris and John Darcy, *The European Social Charter*, 2nd edn, Transnational Publishers, Ardsley 2001, 1–8.

²⁰ PACE, Recommendation, supra n. 9; PACE, Opinion no. 5, 25 September 1953.

²¹ Harris and Darcy, supra n. 19, 5–6.

²² Social Committee of the Council of Ministers of the Council of Europe, «Preliminary Draft of Articles for Possible inclusion in a Social Charter – Working Paper submitted by the United Kingdom Delegation», 27 April 1956, available in: *Collection of Travaux Préparatoires*, Vol. 3 (1956), at 738, <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/preparatory-work>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

²³ Social Committee of the Council of Ministers of the Council of Europe, «Working Party – Memorandum and Draft Texts», 15 September 1957, in: the *Collection of Travaux Préparatoires*, Vol. 4 (1957), at 158, paras 12, 13. Emphasis added.

²⁴ PACE, «Draft European Social, Opinion» Doc. no. 1035, 12 September 1959, <<https://pace.coe.int/en/files/1352/html>>; PACE, Opinion 32, 1960, <<https://pace.coe.int/en/files/13771/html>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

states at the time except Iceland and Austria signed the Charter. The Italian city of Turin has since had a symbolic value within the Charter system, which is reflected in the fact that the 1991 Protocol to the ESC and the “process” launched in 2014 aimed at “strengthening the European Social Charter System within the Council of Europe and in its relationship with the law of the European Union”²⁵ are named after this city.

The second recital locates the Charter as a means of implementation of the aims of the CoE. Indeed, the “maintenance and further realisation of human rights and fundamental freedoms” was identified as an essential method to achieve “greater unity between its members for the purpose of safeguarding and realising the ideals and principles which are their common heritage and of facilitating their economic and social progress”.²⁶ The “ideals and principles which are the common heritage” of the CoE member states, as agreed in the post-Second World War era are generally identified as democracy, the rule of law, pluralism, justice, peace and freedom.²⁷ Unlike the ECHR drafters, the drafters of the Charter did not unpack any element of this “common heritage” in the Preamble, but they did not miss the opportunity to explicitly refer to the fact that the goal of achieving “greater unity” via multilateral initiatives should be functionally linked to the socio-economic progress of the member states of the organisation. In doing so, this recital highlights the motives of the drafting: the idea of a European Social Charter, as highlighted in the *travaux préparatoires*, underscores the fact that regulating labour and social policies or rights was regarded as an interest worth pursuing among the “values of western civilization”.²⁸ Indeed, during “les trente glorieuses”,²⁹ the gradual expansion of labour rights and social programmes was part of a strategy to achieve long-lasting peace and improve standards of living, which were regarded as intertwined political and economic goals for the reconstruction of Europe.³⁰ While this recital refers to the aims and “ideals” of the CoE, the object and purpose of the Charter is better unpacked by other recitals and the values on which the treaty is based have been unpacked by the ECSR over the years and include “dignity, autonomy, equality and solidarity”.³¹ With explicit reference to the Preamble of the Charter of 1961, the ECSR held that “one of the underlying purposes of the social rights protected by the Charter is to express solidarity and promote social inclusion”,³² this being a circumstance that affects treaty interpretation.³³

The second recital also specifies that human rights should be “maintained” and “further realised” as a result of the CoE’s actions and states’ implementation measures. Due to the lack of applicable jurisprudence referring to the Preamble of the ESC on this point and the existence of an identical reference in the Preamble of the ECHR, I refer to the jurisprudence of the ECtHR by way of analogy: “<Maintenance> requires the Court to ensure in particular that the rights and freedoms

²⁵ See information on the Turin Process of the European Social Charter <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/turin-process>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

²⁶ Statute of the CoE, supra n. 11, Article 1(a), (b).

²⁷ Celine Husson-Rochongar, *Droit international des droits de l’homme et valeurs*, Bruylant, Brussels 2012, at 12. Cfr. Statute of the CoE, supra n. 11, Preamble, with Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR) (adopted 4 November 1950 entry into force 3 September 1953) ETS 005, Preamble.

²⁸ Memorandum by the SG, supra n. 10, at 4–5.

²⁹ The French economist Jean Fourastié, *Les Trente glorieuses ou la Révolution invisible*, Fayard, Paris 1979, defined *les trente glorieuses* the thirty years of economic growth between the late 1940s and the early 1970s.

³⁰ Francis G. Castles et al., «Introduction», in : F. G. Castles et al. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of the Welfare State*, OUP, Oxford 2010, at 7–9. See also Preamble of the Statute of the CoE, supra n. 11.

³¹ ECSR, *International Federation of Human Rights Leagues (FIDH) v. France*, Coll. Com. No. 14/2003, decision on the merits of 8 September 2004, para 27.

³² ECSR, *International Federation of Human Rights (FIDH) v. Belgium*, Coll. Com. No. 75/2011, decision of the merits of 18 March 2013.

³³ Bige Açımuz and Olgun Akbulut, «The European Social Charter and Values», in: S. Angeleri and C. Nivard (eds.), *The European Social Charter: A Commentary*, Vol. 1, Brill, Leiden 2021, Forthcoming.

set out in the Convention continue to be effective in changing circumstances. <Further realisation> allows for a degree of innovation and creativity, which may extend the scope of the Convention guarantees”.³⁴ In the context of the Charter, these principles have been operationalised: the ECSR holds that the Charter is “a living instrument” and that “the rights and freedoms set out therein should be interpreted in the light of current conditions and of new emerging issues and situations”.³⁵ However, unlike the ECtHR, the ECSR has not attributed any explicit normative authority to the Preamble as incorporating the Statute of the CoE.

B. The uncertain legal value of the ECHR and UDHR in the preamble of the Charter

The third recital arguably confirms that the purpose of drafting a socio-economic rights convention within the framework of the CoE was to provide a normative counterpart to the ECHR, which protected civil and political rights.³⁶ There is no indication in the *travaux préparatoires* that this provision, referring to the ECHR, was meant to lead to interpretations of the scope of the ESC rights in considerations of the obligations under the ECHR or play any “incorporative function”. The latter is likewise excluded by the use of ‘agreed to secure’ at past tense, which located the ECHR outside the Charter treaty system. However, in accordance with the indivisibility of human rights – which is incorporated into the Preamble of the Revised Charter and discussed below – the ECSR has, in practice, made wide use of the material content of the ECHR, as well as the interpretive techniques of the ECtHR, to develop the scope of both the Charter of 1961 and the Revised Charter in consistency with ECHR obligations.³⁷

At this point, it seems significant to highlight that the Preamble of the Charter – unlike the ECHR and other general human rights treaties that were negotiated and adopted in the decades that immediately followed the Second World War³⁸ – does not contain any mention of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) as a source of moral principles or of “relevant rules and principles of international law and part of the general international law framework” to which European human rights treaties belong.³⁹ The *travaux préparatoires* of the ESC contain some but not many references to the UDHR as “source of inspiration” for the Charter’s rights,⁴⁰ but they do not explicitly state that the Charter is based upon the UDHR.⁴¹ This can be explained by the fact that the Charter – as reflected in its limited personal and geographic scope – was conceived as a particularistic

³⁴ ECtHR, *Stummer v. Austria*, Appl. No. 37452/02, judgment of 7 July 2011, Partly Dissenting Opinion of Judge Tulkens, para 3, citing ECtHR, *Wemhoff v. Germany*, Appl. No. 2122/6427, judgment of 27 June 1968, para 8.

³⁵ ECSR, *Marangopoulos Foundation for Human Rights v. Greece*, Coll. Com. No. 30/2005, decision on the merits of 6 December 2006, para 194; ECSR, *ILGA v. Czech Republic*, Coll. Com. No. 117/2015, decision on the merits of 15 May 2018, para 75.

³⁶ ECSR, Conclusions VII (1978) – Statement of interpretation – Article 13(4), para 1: “The committee noted first that the Charter was designed to be complementary to the European Convention on Human Rights (cf. Preamble)”.

³⁷ See *infra*, Section IV.

³⁸ E.g., see ECHR, *supra* n. 27 Preamble; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (both adopted 16 December 1966 entry into force 23 March 1976) UNGA Res 2200A (XXI), Preambles.

³⁹ Shabas, *supra* n. 13, at 65.

⁴⁰ For instance, PACE, Committee of Social Questions, «Memorandum by the Secretariat of the Committee on the Preliminary Draft of the Social Charter prepared by the Working Party», 5 July 1955, at 105; CM, Social Committee, «European Social Charter (Rights relating to Employment and Working Conditions)», 30 January 1956, at 667–727.

⁴¹ In the *travaux préparatoires* of the ESC, there are several references to the ECHR, as being based upon the UDHR, and regarding the complementary role of the Charter and the ECHR (e.g., PACE, «Common Policy of Member States on Social Matters (debate)», official reports, 23 September 1953, at 16. However only the report of the Tripartite Conference of 1958 (Tripartite Conference Convened by the International Labour Organisation at the Request of the Council of Europe, Strasbourg, 1958, C.S.E.1958, at 174 & 179) mentions that the Charter “may be said to be based...on the UDHR”.

instrument that would contribute to the unity and socio-economic progress of European populations.⁴² Nonetheless, the jurisprudence of the ECSR, in more recent years, positively qualified this approach by stating that the Charter is a “human rights treaty which aims to implement at a European level, as a complement to the European Convention on Human Rights, the rights guaranteed to all human beings by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948”.⁴³

C. Interpretative and supplementary equality-related inputs

The last two recitals are arguably the most interesting passages of this Preamble in terms of legal relevance. They clearly illustrate the object and purpose of the treaty, which include securing the enjoyment of social rights without discrimination while also contributing to the improvement of people’s standards of living in both cities and rural areas. They have been useful standards for the ECSR’s interpretation of state obligations and its monitoring of states’ fulfilment of those obligations.

The final text of the Charter of 1961 does not contain any ad hoc non-discrimination provision. However, such a provision was added to the Preamble at a late stage of its negotiations.⁴⁴ While preambles do not normally establish textual rights and obligations, the Preamble of the Charter of 1961 proved an exception, as the ECSR has employed the fourth recital in conjunction with the substantive articles of the Charter to supplement the duties of the operative part of the treaty and assess alleged discriminatory measures on a number of prohibited grounds. Included in such cases⁴⁵ is that of *ERTF v Czech Republic*, where the complainant organisation alleged that the responding state had insufficiently protected the rights to health care and family housing of Romani people in Czechia. The ECSR found that the unaddressed residential segregation of these people in inadequate and unhealthy living conditions, as well as their restricted access to health services, constituted violations of “Article 11 (right to protection of health) and 16 (the right of the family to social, legal and economic protection) of the 1961 Charter in light of its Preamble”.⁴⁶ Similarly, in two cases against Greece, the ECSR held that there was a “violation of Article 4§1 (right to a fair remuneration) in the light of the non-discrimination clause of the Preamble of the 1961 Charter as the reduction of the minimum wage for workers under 25 years [was] excessive and constitute[d] discrimination on grounds of age”.⁴⁷

While complainants continue to bring cases before the ECSR alleging violations of this recital of the Preamble of the Charter of 1961⁴⁸ by states who have not ratified the Revised Charter, a recent decision of the ECSR seems to cast doubt on the normative strength of the preambular non-

⁴² Appendix to the European Social Charter, supra n. 3, paras 1, 2.

⁴³ ECSR, *EUROCEF v. France*, Coll. Com. No. 114/2015, decision on the merits of 24 January 2018, para 53. See also ECSR, Conclusions 2006 – Statement of interpretation – Comments of a general nature, 2006_Ob_1-1/Ob/EN.

⁴⁴ Cfr. CM, «Report of the Social Committee», 10 February 1958, CM58/18, para 107; «Text submitted by the CM to the Tripartite Conference», supra n. 41, at 185; PACE, supra n. 24 and ESC, supra n. 3, Preamble.

⁴⁵ ECSR, *INTERRIGHTS v. Croatia*, Coll. Com. No. 45/2007, decision on the merits of 30 March 2009, paras 60, 61, for violation of Article 11(2) in the light of the non-discrimination clause of the Preamble to the Charter because state practices constituted discrimination on the ground of sexual orientation in the enjoyment of the right to health education; ECSR, *Centre on Housing Rights and Evictions v. Croatia (COHRE)*, Coll. Com. No. 52/2008 decision on the merits of 22 June 2010, para 89, for violation of Article 16 of the Charter in the light of the non-discrimination clause of the Preamble, on the “grounds that the <ethnic Serb> population displaced during the conflict in the former Yugoslavia has been subjected to disproportionate discriminatory treatment regarding their housing needs”.

⁴⁶ ECSR, *ERTF v. Czech Republic*, Coll. Com. No. 104/2014, decision on the merits of 17 May 2016, paras 79, 112, 128.

⁴⁷ ECSR, *Greek General Confederation of Labour (GSEE) v. Greece*, Coll. Com. No. 111/2014, decision on the merits of 23 March 2017, paras 194–197, *GENOP-DEI and ADEDY v. Greece*, Coll. Com. No. 66/2011, decision on the merits of 23 May 2012, paras 66–69.

⁴⁸ ECSR, *European Federation of National Organisations working with the Homeless (FEANTSA) v. Czech Republic*, Coll. Com. No. 191/2020, decision on admissibility of 9 December 2020; ECSR, *European Roma Rights Centre (ERRC) v. Czech Republic*, Coll. Com. No. 190/2020, decision on admissibility of 9 September 2020.

discrimination rule. In *Transgender Europe and ILGA-Europe v. Czech Republic*, the complainants argued that the “legal requirement of sterilisation imposed on trans people wishing to change their personal documents so that they reflect their gender identity”, in the responding state, violates Article 11 ESC, “either alone or in light of the non-discrimination clause of the Preamble”, on the grounds that such “a major medical procedure, with irreversible consequences for a person’s health, especially reproductive health, self-conception and mental wellbeing” is not required of “cisgender people, whose gender identity is readily recognized at birth without the need to undergo sterilisation”.⁴⁹ The Committee substantially accepted all the arguments of the complaint – including that the “condition attached for the recognition of transgender person’s gender identity vitiates free consent” and that such a “situation is [...] discriminatory on grounds of gender identity” – and decided against the state.⁵⁰ However, it concluded by stating, “as the complaint has been lodged under the 1961 Charter the Committee will not consider the complaint in light of the Preamble to the 1961 Charter”.⁵¹ This approach, which judge Lukas in her concurring opinion called “rather formalistic [and...] difficult to understand given the facts of the case”,⁵² seems to indicate reduced normative force of the Preamble vis-à-vis Article E of the Revised Charter. Comparing and contrasting these two non-discrimination clauses, it is also worth point out that the Preamble of the Charter employed the word ‘should’ whereas Article E of the Revised Charter uses the stronger ‘shall’ to refer to Charter-related state duties of non-discrimination. Indeed, the insertion of the principle of non-discrimination into “a separate article in the Revised Charter indicate[d] the heightened importance the drafters paid to the principle of non-discrimination with respect to the achievement of the various substantive rights contained therein”, regardless of any difference based on a non-exhaustive number of grounds.⁵³

The last recital of this Preamble, read in conjunction with others, is also indicative of the object and purpose of the treaty with qualifiers of the obligations that states assume when signing up to the Charter.⁵⁴ The ESC system, including its reporting procedure, is part of a multilateral and intersectoral strategy that CoE’s state parties undertake (as “effort in common”), which aims to “improve the standard of living and promote the social well-being of both their urban and rural populations”. This outcome, which is of a programmatic nature, is qualified by an obligation of conduct that requires states to equitably target their entire population and, thus, to disaggregate their development and welfare policies. In its reporting procedure, the ECSR has raised many concerns regarding disparities between or a lack of disaggregated information on urban and rural areas in terms of the enjoyment of virtually all ESC substantive rights. For instance, particularly critical issues have been raised regarding unequal access to health services,⁵⁵ a lack of special measures targeting child labour in rural areas⁵⁶ and unequal socio-economic protection of women, children and families (e.g., due to a shortage of shelters for victims of domestic violence and inadequate childcare benefits and facilities).⁵⁷ Given that the Preamble of the Charter of 1961 contains the only textual references to the terms “urban and rural” in the entire ESC treaty system and in the light of the jurisprudence of

⁴⁹ *Transgender Europe and ILGA-Europe*, supra n. 35, paras 10, 51, 55.

⁵⁰ *ibid.*, paras 86, 87

⁵¹ *ibid.*, para 88.

⁵² *ibid.*, Separate concurring opinion of Karin Lukas.

⁵³ ECSR, *International Association Autism-Europe (IAAE) v. France*, Coll Com No. 13/2002, decision on the merits of 4 November 2003, para 51.

⁵⁴ Section IV, infra, will specifically address the issue of the nature of ESC-related obligations.

⁵⁵ 89 applicable results (40 regarding the Charter of 1961 and 49 regarding the Revised Charter) in HUDOC-ESC database, filtering the research by ‘conclusions’, ‘article 11’, key word: Rural.

⁵⁶ 42 applicable results (6 regarding the Charter of 1961 and 36 regarding the Revised Charter) in HUDOC-ESC database, filtering the research by ‘conclusions’, ‘article 7’, key word: Rural.

⁵⁷ 65 applicable results (10 regarding the Charter of 1961 and 55 regarding the Revised Charter) in HUDOC-ESC database, filtering the research by ‘conclusions’, ‘article 16’, ‘article 17’, key word: Rural.

the ECSR, it can be inferred that it has played an important, although indirect,⁵⁸ role in guiding the monitoring of the domestic implementation of both Charters.

III. The ESC Protocols – The Portrayal of a Treaty System in Need of Substantive and Procedural Revisions

Table 2. The Preamble of the Additional Protocol of 1988 (ETS No. 128) – “four new rights”	
1	The member States of the Council of Europe signatory hereto,
2	Resolved to take new measures to extend the protection of the social and economic rights guaranteed by the European Social Charter, opened for signature in Turin on 18 October 1961 (hereinafter referred to as ‘the Charter’),
3	Have agreed as follows:

Table 3. The Preamble of the Amending Protocol of 1991 (ETS No.142) – “revisions to the reporting system”	
1	The member States of the Council of Europe, signatory to this Protocol to the European Social Charter, opened for signature in Turin on 18 October 1961 (hereinafter referred to as ‘the Charter’),
2	Being resolved to take some measures to improve the effectiveness of the Charter, and particularly the functioning of its supervisory machinery;
3	Considering therefore that it is desirable to amend certain provisions of the Charter,
4	Have agreed as follows:

Table 4. The Preamble of the Additional Protocol of 1995 (ETS No.158) – “establishment of the collective complaint procedure”	
1	The member States of the Council of Europe, signatories to this Protocol to the European Social Charter, opened for signature in Turin on 18 October 1961 (hereinafter referred to as ‘the Charter’),
2	Resolved to take new measures to improve the effective enforcement of the social rights guaranteed by the Charter;
3	Considering that this aim could be achieved in particular by the establishment of a collective complaints procedure, which, inter alia, would strengthen the participation of management and labour and of non-governmental organisations,
4	Have agreed as follows:

The Preambles to these three Protocols, considered together, tell us that the human rights framework set up by the Charter of 1961 and the promises of its Preamble had not lived up to expectations. As such, they are prevalently of historical value for outlining the motives of the reform process.

Indeed, as early as 1978, the member states of the CoE declared it their priority to “explor[e] the possibility of extending the lists of [genuinely enforceable] rights of the individual, notably rights in the social, economic and cultural field”.⁵⁹ The Steering Committee for Social Affairs (CDSO), which was instructed by the Committee of Ministers to take the lead in this process, after one year of periodic meetings, decided to discard the proposal to add a socio-economic rights protocol to the ECHR because of lack of agreement on the justiciability of social rights.⁶⁰ A general lack of enthusiasm, in the 1980s, among states in the CDSO led to the adoption of a very modest additional

⁵⁸ On the implicit relevance of the preambles on the ECSR’s jurisprudence, see also Nikolaos A Papadopoulos, «Revisiting the Preamble of the European Social Charter: Paper Tiger or Blessing in Disguise?» Human Rights Law Review (2021), 1–21, at 8.

⁵⁹ Explanatory Report to the Additional Protocol to the European Social Charter, Strasbourg, 5 May 1988, para 1, referring to the CoE’s member states’ Declaration on Human Rights of 27 April 1978.

⁶⁰ Vivien Shrusball, «The Additional Protocol to the European Social Charter – Employment Rights» 18(1) Industrial Law Journal (1989), 39–53, at 40.

protocol at the end of that decade, which added four substantive rights to those already agreed upon in the Charter of 1961.⁶¹ The second recital of the Preamble to the 1988 Additional Protocol briefly unpacks the motive behind the adoption of this instrument: the need to “take new measures to extend the protection of the social and economic rights”⁶² to align the Charter system to the “socio-economic development” that had occurred since the Charter of 1961 was adopted.⁶³ Although the Preamble to the 1988 Protocol characterises this treaty as “an <extension> of the Charter”, it also specifies that it is “nonetheless legally independent” of the Charter.⁶⁴

The Preamble of the 1991 Protocol clearly establishes that the purpose of the instrument is to promote the adoption of “some” measures to “improve the effectiveness” of the Charter. Likewise, the Preamble to the 1995 Protocol specifies the adoption of “new” measures to ensure the Charter’s “effective enforcement”.⁶⁵ Indeed, the most striking and indeed the most criticised difference between the ESC and the ECHR concerned their monitoring and accountability mechanisms: the Charter was monitored via a lengthy and politicised reporting procedures in which the role of NGOs and trade unions was limited and that of individuals non-existent,⁶⁶ whereas the ECHR provided for a system of individual and state petitions.

On 5 November 1990, at an informal ministerial conference of human rights, the attendees – ministers representing the CoE member states – decided that it was important to “give the Charter a fresh impetus”.⁶⁷ A few weeks later, the Committee of Ministers of the CoE established an ad hoc committee, the Charte-Rel Committee, to suggest proposals for improving the effectiveness of the Charter, particularly with regard to the supervision of the treaty.⁶⁸

In the three meetings held in 1991, a proposal to strengthen the reporting system was discussed and then adopted in the form of an Amending Protocol. This Protocol has not yet entered into force, as it requires the ratification of all ESC state parties.⁶⁹ Nonetheless, following from the exhortative third recital of its Preamble, which states that “it is desirable to amend certain provisions of the Charter”, the Committee of Ministers has asked the “States party to the Charter and the supervisory bodies to envisage the application of certain of the measures provided for in this Protocol before its entry into force, in so far as the text of the Charter will allow”.⁷⁰ As a result of this “informal” agreement between the parties concerned, most of the amendments to the articles concerning the compulsory reporting procedure of the Charter of 1961 (which are recalled in the Revised Charter) have currently been applied.⁷¹

Subsequently, in 1992, the Charte-Rel Committee, in collaboration with the ECSR and relevant steering committees, began to discuss proposals for a collective complaints procedure, which eventually resulted in the 1995 Additional Protocol.⁷² This solution was clearly the result of a

⁶¹ Harris and Darcy, *supra* n. 19, at 11.

⁶² Additional Protocol (1988), *supra* n. 3, Preamble.

⁶³ Explanatory Report, *supra* n. 58, para 21.

⁶⁴ *ibid.*, para 10.

⁶⁵ Amending Protocol (1991) and Additional Protocol (1995), *supra* n. 3, Preamble, recital 2.

⁶⁶ François Vandamme, «The Revision of the European Social Charter» 133(5-6) *International Labour Review* (1994), 635–655, at 639, 641.

⁶⁷ Explanatory Report to the Protocol amending the European Social Charter, Turin, 21 October 1991, para 1; DAVID HARRIS, *supra* n. 1, at 659-676.

⁶⁸ CM, «Decision No. 498/051290 on the Committee on the European Social Charter – Charte-rel.», 5 December 1990, 449th meeting of the Ministers’ Deputies.

⁶⁹ Amending Protocol (1991), *supra* n. 3, Article 8.

⁷⁰ CM, «Conclusions of the 467th Meeting of the Ministers’ Deputies», CM/Del/Dec(91)467, 11 December 1991, item 11, at 41.

⁷¹ This is in line with the VCLT, *supra* n. 16, Article 25(1)(b): “A treaty or a part of a treaty is applied provisionally pending its entry into force if [...] the negotiating States have in some other manner so agreed”.

⁷² CHARTE-REL Committee, «Final Activity Report», Charte-Rel (94) 23, 19 October 1994, at 1–4.

compromise between those members of the Charte-Rel Committee that demanded or suggested an individual complaint mechanism and the majority of CoE states which had never considered such a mechanism viable for socio-economic rights.⁷³ Against this background, the Preamble to the 1995 Additional (and optional) Protocol spells out the greatest achievement of this reform to the supervisory mechanism: the “strengthen[ing of] the participation of management and labour and of non-governmental organisations”.⁷⁴ This recital encapsulates years of discussion and frustrations regarding the role of trade unions and NGOs in the context of the supervision of the ESC-related obligations. For instance, while the role of social partners and NGOs had only been modestly increased by the Protocol of 1991,⁷⁵ the 1995 Protocol specified these organisations as the only admitted complainants of the new collective complaint procedure. However, the Preamble’s brief mention of motives does not specify the actual limits of the involvement of some of these actors and may, therefore, seem merely ceremonial. Indeed, the actual rules of the operative parts of the Protocol limit the normative force of this apparently extensive recital. Indeed, according to Articles 1 and 2 of the Protocol, the organisations that can file a collective complaint are 1) international employers’ organisations and trade unions, which act as observers in the national reporting context; 2) international NGOs that have consultative status with the CoE and that are on a list established for this purpose by the Governmental Committee;⁷⁶ 3) *representative* national organisations of employers and trade unions from within the jurisdiction of the respondent state;⁷⁷ and 4) (optionally for states) “representative” and “particularly competent” *national* NGOs.⁷⁸ Therefore, with the regards to the power to file complaints before the ECSR, the position of NGOs is not equalised with that of trade unions and employers’ organisations. While it has been argued that the limited role granted to NGOs deprives the Charter’s supervisory mechanism of a useful element,⁷⁹ the establishment of the collective complaints mechanism has fundamentally changed the supervision of the Charter, enabling the supervisory bodies to intervene in urgent or specific situations.⁸⁰

Overall, the Preambles to the Protocols are very short; they briefly encapsulate the system reform-related motivations that led states to adopt them, but, given their low level of detail vis-à-vis the operational parts of the respective treaties (in particular the procedural articles of Protocols of 1991 and 1996), they are arguably too generic to play any normative role in treaty interpretation.

IV. The Revised Charter – An Updated Treaty that Reinforces the Indivisibility of Rights

Table 5. The Preamble of the European Social Charter (Revised) of 1996 (ETS. No. 163)

⁷³ Paolo Pucci Di Benischi, «Reforms of the Charter Since 1989 – Reform of the Supervisory Machinery and Reform of the Rights Guaranteed’ in: Secretariat of the Council of Europe, *The Social Charter of the 21st Century*, CoE Publishing, Strasbourg 1997, 39–65, at 49.

⁷⁴ Additional Protocol (1995), supra n. 3, Preamble,

⁷⁵ Amending Protocol (1991), supra n. 3, Article 1 amends Article 23 ESC to the extent that now states must submit their periodic report to national trade unions and representatives of employers, and these social partners can send supplementary information to the Secretary General. National NGOs are not recipients of any duty to report. Furthermore, the Secretary General will forward a copy of the reports to the international non-governmental organisations having consultative status with the CoE but these organisations cannot submit any observations. It is just a duty to report.

⁷⁶ The current list was updated in January 2019, see «List of INGOs entitled to submit collective complaints», GC(2019)1, <<https://rm.coe.int/gc-2019-1-bil-list-ingos-01-01-2019/1680947cd7>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

⁷⁷ E.g., see ECSR, *Confédération française de l’Encadrement “CFE-CGC” v. France*, Coll. Com. No. 9/2000, decision on the merits of 16 November 2007, para 6.

⁷⁸ Additional Protocol (1995), supra n. 3, Article 2(1). As of September 2020, only Finland has made such declaration.

⁷⁹ DI BENISCHI, supra n. 72, at 48.

⁸⁰ *ibid.*, at 51. See also, Markus Jaeger, «The Additional Protocol to the ESC Providing for a System of Collective Complaints» 10(1) *Leiden Journal of International Law* (2004), 69–80; Regis Brillat, «The Supervisory Machinery of the European Social Charter: Recent Developments and their Impact’», in: G. De Búrca & B. De Witte, supra n. 1, at 31.

1	Same as the ESC of 1961- “The governments signatory [...]”
2	Same as the ESC of 1961 – “Considering that the aim of the Council of Europe is [...]”
3	Same as the ESC of 1961 – “Considering that in the [ECHR] [...] member states [...] agreed to secure [...] civil and political rights”
4	Considering that in the European Social Charter opened for signature in Turin on 18 October 1961 and the Protocols thereto, the member States of the Council of Europe agreed to secure to their populations the social rights specified therein in order to improve their standard of living and their social well-being;
5	Recalling that the Ministerial Conference on Human Rights held in Rome on 5 November 1990 stressed the need, on the one hand, to preserve the indivisible nature of all human rights, be they civil, political, economic, social or cultural and, on the other hand, to give the European Social Charter fresh impetus;
6	Resolved, as was decided during the Ministerial Conference held in Turin on 21 and 22 October 1991, to update and adapt the substantive contents of the Charter in order to take account in particular of the fundamental social changes which have occurred since the text was adopted;
7	Recognising the advantage of embodying in a Revised Charter, designed progressively to take the place of the European Social Charter, the rights guaranteed by the Charter as amended, the rights guaranteed by the Additional Protocol of 1988 and to add new rights,
8	Have agreed as follows:

The Preamble to the Revised Charter of 1996 is almost twice as long as the Preamble of the Charter of 1961. It provides qualifiers regarding the nature of human rights obligations under the Charter – which are useful for treaty interpretation – and offers a relatively detailed overview of the motivations for and landmark events of the reform process that led to the adoption of this new treaty.

A. The indicative nature of the ESC-related obligations

The first three recitals are the same of those of the Charter of 1961 and I refer to the discussion conducted in section II. However, it is worth noting that the comparison between the third recital concerning the acknowledgement of the ECHR and the fourth recital on the ESC of 1961 indicates, more clearly than in the Preamble of the original Charter, that these instruments have equal status in “securing”, respectively, civil rights and social rights in Europe. In doing so, however, the wording seems to suggest that civil and political rights and fundamental freedoms are valued human interests in themselves, while social rights are functional for “improv[ing] the standards of living and social wellbeing” of the population of the state parties.⁸¹ Notwithstanding this distinction, I would like to draw attention to the parallel use of the word “secure” with regard to civil and social rights, which in ordinary English means “to ensure the safety of; to protect”,⁸² as confirmed by the French version of the Revised Charter: “assurer ... les droits...”.⁸³ This is a tangible clue as to the nature of the obligations that both Charters created for state parties who accept their Part II provisions. Unlike the case of the UN International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights, which limits the implementation of international obligations to the availability of a “state’s economic and other [...] resources” and generally requires the progressive realisation of socio-economic rights, the Charter urges state parties to satisfy the Charter standards set out in the accepted articles or paragraphs, in principle, irrespective of their national resources and immediately upon ratification. However, it should be noted that this is not the case for some Charter rights, which are classed as “dynamic” and

⁸¹ ESC (Revised), supra n. 3, Preamble, recital 4.

⁸² Oxford English Dictionary, «Secure, v.», <<https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/174648?rskey=uMErDp&result=3&isAdvanced=false#eid>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021).

⁸³ Charte sociale européenne (révisée), supra n 3, Préambule.

require progressive realisation.⁸⁴ Accordingly, most of ESC provisions establish “obligations of result, which implies that when a provision is accepted by a contracting party, the right involved must be guaranteed” in law, policies and practice “then and there”.⁸⁵ Such demanding implementation duties are counterbalanced by the “à-la-carte” approach that limits the binding effects of the entire treaty for state parties.

B. “Indivisibility” for treaty interpretation and the enhanced role of the ECHR

The above remarks are also significant in consideration of the fifth recital’s reference to the “indivisible nature of all human rights”, which restates the importance of considering the rights of the Charter on an equal basis with civil rights and fundamental freedoms. Conceiving them as interdependent with each other and with the rights contained in other human rights instruments, most notably those of the ECHR, was part of the strategy to give “fresh impetus” to the Social Charter in the CoE’s legal framework. It should not be forgotten that the Revised Charter was being negotiated by the Charte-Rel Committee between 1992 and 1994, during which time the pivotal Vienna’s World Conference on Human Rights held in 1993 solemnly declared, “All human rights are universal, indivisible and interdependent and interrelated. The international community must treat human rights globally in a fair and equal manner, on the same footing, and with the same emphasis”.⁸⁶

The ECSR elaborated on this and other preambular recitals by stating, “The Social Charter is a human rights treaty. Its purpose is to apply the Universal Declaration of Human Rights within Europe [and, in doing so, to] complement to the European Convention on Human Rights. It reflects the concern of countries that have ratified it to give real meaning to the notion of the indivisibility and interdependence of human rights”.⁸⁷

For instance, this principle was operationalised as a principle of interpretation regarding the rights of refugees, whom, the ECSR clarified, were entitled to the same “fundamental rights of every human being which [...] are universal, indivisible and interdependent. The social and economic integration of every individual is an essential part of their right to lead a dignified life”.⁸⁸ Furthermore, the indivisible and interconnected nature of all human rights in both the ESC and the ECHR contributed to the ground-breaking decision, by the ECSR, that excluding irregular migrant children from the scope of the Charter’s right to medical care – irregular migrants are textually excluded from the personal scope of both Charters by their Appendix – would affect the achievement of “the overall purpose of the Charter”, which is to “give life and meaning to fundamental social rights” and would threaten the protection of the “interconnected rights to life and to the preservation of human dignity”.⁸⁹

The application of this interpretive principle has facilitated a contextual and purposive interpretation of the Charter rights, which are considered indivisible and interdependent with those

⁸⁴ For instance, see ESC, *supra* n. 3, Article 12(3); For further analysis, see Donna Gomien, David Harris and Leo Zwaak, *Law and Practice of the European Convention on Human Rights and the European Social Charter* (CoE Publishing, Strasbourg 1996), at 380, 381; HARRIS & DARCY, *supra* n. 19, at 26, 27.

⁸⁵ Stein Evju, «Application by Domestic Courts of the European Social Charter» 28(3–4) *Nordic Journal of Human Rights* (2010), 401–421, at 406.

⁸⁶ World Conference on Human Rights, Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action Vienna (12 July 1993) A/CONF.157/23, para 5.

⁸⁷ ECSR, *Conclusions 2006*, *supra* n. 43.

⁸⁸ ECSR, *Conclusions 2015 – Statement of interpretation – The rights of refugees under the Charter*, 2015_163_10/EN.

⁸⁹ ECSR, *FIDH v. France*, *supra* n. 31, paras 27–32. Emphasis added.

emerging from other treaties, particularly with those of the ECHR.⁹⁰ For example, to resolve controversies, the ECSR has stressed the interconnected nature of the rights to vote and to social inclusion,⁹¹ the rights to health and to respect for private life,⁹² and the rights to socio-economic protection of children and to freedom from ill-treatment.⁹³ This interconnectedness also applies to the articles of the ESC itself, as “the Charter was conceived as a whole and all its provisions complement each other and overlap in part”.⁹⁴ Even though the principle of indivisibility is clearly spelled out only in the Preamble of the Revised Charter, it is also applied in relation to controversies on the interpretation and implementation of the Charter of 1961.⁹⁵ Therefore, the third recital of both Charters’ Preambles, in the light of the practice, should not be dismissed as simple acknowledgements of the ECHR as the most well-known CoE’s treaty that the Charter complements; instead, in relation to the remarks on the indivisible nature of all human rights, these preambular references constitute a clear invitation to the ECSR and states to embrace a systematic and purposive approach to treaty interpretation in order to extend the personal and material scope of the Charter.⁹⁶

C. Explaining a complex treaty system

The sixth recital of the Preamble of the Revised Charter also specifies the motives and purpose of this key addition to the ESC system: “updating and adopting the substantive contents of the [original] Charter” to “take account of the development of labour law and social policies” that had occurred since the adoption of the Charter of 1961⁹⁷ and that the Protocol of 1998 had been unable to fully address. For example, neither the Charter of 1961 nor the Protocol of 1988 provide for any right to housing or education. Instead of adopting another additional protocol, the Charte-Rel Committee opted for an autonomous instrument, which includes – as clarified in the seventh recital of the Preamble – the original rights of the ESC of 1961, at times amended in both their headings and normative content, those included in the Protocol of 1988, and new rights. While the ESC system accepts the coexistence of the two Charters, and the relationship between the two Charters for states who have ratified both is regulated in the operational part of the treaty,⁹⁸ the Preamble overtly states that the Revised Charter is “designed [to] progressively [...] take the place of the European Social Charter” of 1961.⁹⁹ This programmatic invitation issued in the Preamble has been taken up by most of the states of the CoE. To date, of the 43 CoE member states that are parties to either version of the

⁹⁰ Regarding the influence of the case law of the ECtHR on the jurisprudence of the ECSR, in terms of interpretive principles and concepts, see ECSR, «Digest of the Case Law of the European Committee of Social Rights», December 2018, at 40–46.

⁹¹ ECSR, *European Roma Rights Centre (ERRC) v. France*, Coll. Com. No. 51/2008, decision on the merits of 19 October 2009, para 99; ECSR, *European Roma and Travellers Forum (ERTF) v. France*, Coll. Com. No. 64/2011, decision on the merits of 24 January 2012, para 71.

⁹² ECSR, *Transgender Europe and ILGA-Europe*, supra n. 35, para 83.

⁹³ ECSR, *International Commission of Jurists (ICJ) v. Czech Republic*, Coll. Com. No.148/2017, decision on the merits of 20 October 2020, paras 42–44.

⁹⁴ ECSR, *Mental Disability Advocacy Center (MDAC) v. Bulgaria*, Coll. Com. No. 41/2007, decision on the merits of 3 June 2008, para 9.

⁹⁵ *Transgender Europe and ILGA-Europe*, supra n. 35; *ICJ*, supra n. 93.

⁹⁶ Certain scholars have gone even further by describing the preambular reference to the ECHR as performing an “incorporative” function. For instance, see Papadopoulos, supra n. 58, at 14.

⁹⁷ ESC (Revised), supra n. 3, Preamble, recital 6; Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3 May 1996, para 8.

⁹⁸ ESC (Revised), supra n. 3, Part III, Article B(2).

⁹⁹ *ibid.*, Preamble, recital 7.

Charter, 37 of them have ratified the Revised Charter and are bound by its normative force, within the limit of accepted provisions.¹⁰⁰

The last remark that is worth making is that the Preamble to the Revised Charter does not embed the non-discrimination principle, as it is now specifically framed as an autonomous provision in Article E of Part V of the treaty. The drafters favoured a general non-discrimination clause inspired by Article 14 of the ECHR over other options.¹⁰¹ Thus, under Article E of the Revised Charter, the enjoyment of all the Charter's rights is to be ensured "without discrimination on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national extraction or social origin, health, association with a national minority, birth or other status".¹⁰² The number of these prohibited grounds has increased vis-à-vis the Preamble of the Charter of 1961, and the list is, in any case, not exhaustive.¹⁰³

V. Conclusions: The Actual and Potential Role of the Preamble of the Charter Treaties

This paper showed that the Preambles of the treaties composing the ESC system are fit to perform both descriptive and normative functions. These Preambles have, first and foremost, highlighted the historical motives and shared ideals behind the drafting and revising of these treaties by European states during the second half of the 20th century and, in particular, the mutual relationships between the promotion of social progress, the achievement of greater unity between the democracies of the CoE and the realisation of human rights. By touching upon the motives of these multilateral initiatives and sketching the context and value system of the treaty, the Charters' preambles expose the treaty's object and purpose, which is to secure an effective, equitable and non-discriminatory enjoyment of social rights (in their interdependent relationships with other human rights), and this has been reflected in the interpretive and supervisory practice of the ECSR.

Preambles have indeed legal relevance in international law,¹⁰⁴ and the European Social Charter is not an exception to this rule. However, not all the preamble recitals are either suitable to affect treaty interpretation or were actually employed as sources of law or interpretive principles. Those of the Protocols of 1988, 1991 and 1995 are short, generic and merely describe the motivations for the reform process. Furthermore, while considerations regarding the realisation of ECHR rights and the indivisibility and interrelatedness of rights have triggered an overall consistent, contextual and purposive interpretation of the Charter rights, the fact that these concepts are only contained in the text of Charters' preambles was acknowledged by the ECSR only on certain occasions, and their authoritative force is at best implied. A more explicit interpretative and even supplementary function is played by the Preamble of the 1961 Charter: its last two recitals state, respectively, that state obligations must be implemented equally in rural and urban areas and emphasise the cross-cutting principle of non-discrimination. Although the latter is not a self-standing right, the ECSR has used it to monitor the implementation of the Charter's rights.

Jointly considering that the VCLT has "placed no limits" on the legal power of preambles,¹⁰⁵ that the Preambles of the ESC treaty system clearly do not consist of empty phrases and contain some

¹⁰⁰ See 'signatures and ratifications' on the website of the European Social Charter, <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/signatures-ratifications>> (last accessed on 2 June 2021). Lichtenstein, Monaco, San Marino and Switzerland are the only CoE'S member states who are not parties to any of the Charters.

¹⁰¹ Charte-Rel –Activity Report, supra n. 71, 'Appendix IV - Proposals examined by the Charte-Rel committee at its 7th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 11th and 12th meetings (...1993 and ... 1994) Group A. Non-discrimination in access to employment and generally', at 2–4.

¹⁰² ESC (Revised), supra n. 3, Article E.

¹⁰³ Explanatory Report to the Revised Charter, supra n. 97, para 136.

¹⁰⁴ VCLT, supra n. 16; Charles Rousseau, *Droit International Public*, I, *Introductions et Sources*, Sirey, Paris 1970, at 87; Jann K. Kleffner, «Auto-referrals and the Complementary Nature of the ICC», in: in C. Stahn & G. Sluiter (eds.), *The Emerging Practice of the International Criminal Court*, Brill, Leiden 2009, 41–53, at p. 45.

¹⁰⁵ Hulme, supra n. 17, at 1343.

important qualifiers for state obligations, that the Charter system for the protection and monitoring of social rights is constantly under either reform and revitalisation processes,¹⁰⁶ the emphasis on the normative role of the preambles of the Charter treaties should be a worth pursuing strategy to enhance social rights jurisprudence in Europe. Indeed, the few references to the preambles of the Charter by the ECSR jurisprudence, where concepts such as indivisibility and interrelatedness of rights and treaty systems are concerned, are a missed opportunity to enhance the normative legitimacy of the findings of the ECSR, which are non-binding, vis-à-vis state implementation. Given that the Charters have not fully lived up to all expectations that its drafters envisaged in its preambles, 60 and 25 years ago respectively, a greater reliance on clear preambular clauses would embed layers of legal reasonings based on text-context analysis, in treaty interpretation, and contribute to achieve the object and purpose of the “social constitution of Europe”.

¹⁰⁶ For instance, see Turin Process, supra n 25, and 1st meeting of the High-Level Group of Experts on Social Rights, press release 9 February 2021, <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-social-charter/-/1st-meeting-of-the-high-level-group-of-experts-on-social-rights>> (last accessed 2 June 2021); PACE, «Overcoming the socio-economic crisis sparked by the Covid-19 pandemic», Report, Committee on Social Affairs, Health and Sustainable Development, 20 May 2021; CM, «The Strategic Framework of the Council of Europe and forthcoming activities», Decision, CM/Del/Dec(2021)131/2a, 21 May 2021.